

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE FLORA OF THE ABSHERON PENINSULA AND THE OIL-CONTAMINATED FLORA OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The wild flora polluted by oil, as well as oil products and groundwater in Azerbaijan, was formed by the geographical location of the mines, relief, soil-ecological conditions, anthropogenic factors and technogenic effects.

In the "Siyazanneft", "Absheronneft" Oil and Gas Extraction Department (NGPC), as well as in the "Buzovna-Mashtaga field" and "Babazanan oil field", as well as in the research objects of the State Oil Company of Azerbaijan (SOCAR), salinized gray-brown, gray-brown grass, the flora contaminated with oil in saline, sandy and marshy soils was studied.

Keywords: taxon, family, genus, species, endemic, subendemic.

"Synopsis of the flora of the areas polluted by oil and oil products in Azerbaijan" was prepared for the first time based on the results of floristic studies conducted in 2021-2024 together with phytoecological studies.

According to A. Akhundova, from the analysis of the wild flora of the Absheron peninsula and the flora of oil-polluted areas in Azerbaijan, it is found that 501 species belonging to 69 families and 301 genera are found in the wild flora of the peninsula. (table 1)

Table 1

Taxa and life forms	In Flora of the Absheron Peninsula		In the flora of oil-contaminated areas in Azerbaijan	
	quantity	in %	quantity	in %
Family	69	100	39	56,5
Genus	301	100	134	44,5
Species	511	100	187	36,6
Tree, shrub, semi-shrub, bush, half bush	56	100	34	60,7
Herbs (multiennial, annual, biennial)	451	100	153	33,9

As shown in Table No. 1, the flora of oil-contaminated areas in Azerbaijan includes 39 families, 134 genera and 187 species according to systematic taxa, as well as shrubs, semi-shrubs, shrubs, semi-shrubs (with 34 species); grasses are represented, including perennials, biennials and annuals (with 153 species).

The analysis of the flora of the oil-contaminated areas in Azerbaijan according to systematic taxa shows that 9 families with the largest number of genera are quantitatively superior. As mentioned, Chenopodiaceae, Asteraceae and Poaceae families occupy the first, second and third place in terms of quantity.

In this sense, it corresponds to the first place (17 breeds) or 12.7%, the second place (17 breeds) and the third place (21 breeds) or 15.7%. Chenopodiaceae (29 species), Asteraceae (24 species) and Poaceae participate in the systematic structure with 22 species or 11.8%. Plant life forms or biomorphs [18, 14, 10] are identified in the flora of the investigated oil-contaminated mining areas.

From the biomorphological analysis, it was found that 103 species (55.1%) of therophytes, 34 species of hemicryptophytes (18.2%) and 21 species of

chamephytes (11.2%) are found in the wild flora of oil-polluted areas.

We identified the plants distributed in the flora of the investigated oil-contaminated mining areas according to five ecological groups [10] based on their water demand. The ecological group of oil-polluted flora consists of xerophytes 111 species and halophytes 37 species, mesoxerophytes 24 species, mesophytes 8 species and hydrophytes 7 species.

According to the studies [17, 6, 7] on the presence of endemic and subendemic species spread in the oil-polluted flora of Azerbaijan, the species included in the "Red Book" have been listed.

The investigation of oil-contaminated flora in Azerbaijan from endemic and subendemic point of view is of important phytoecological importance. Thus, Caucasian endemics (13 species) make up 2.3% of endemics in the flora of the republic, Azerbaijani endemics with 9 species (5.0%) and subendemics with 7 species (1.7%). According to literature information, 7 species (2.6%) of rare, endangered species whose names are included in the "Red Book" [2, 3] have been identified in the flora of the studied oil-contaminated areas.

In general, the names of plants found in the wild flora of oil-polluted areas are represented by 2.6% of the species included in the "Red Book of Azerbaijan".

Planting of the above-mentioned endemic, sub-endemic and main species listed in the "Red Book", especially ecomorphic plants, in the biological reclamation of oil-contaminated lands in Azerbaijan is purposeful. In this regard, measures should be taken to restore the wild flora of oil fields.

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